

ORGANIZATION OF THE SUPERVISORY BOARD WORK IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

M.E.Rustamova

Institute for Retraining and Professional Development of Directors and
Specialists of Preschool Educational Institutions

Associate Professor of the Department of "Preschool Education
Methodology"

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The Supervisory Board of a preschool educational institution is a strategic body that determines the priorities for improving the material and technical base of the preschool educational institution and its development.

It carries out the tasks assigned to the head of the state preschool educational institution regarding measures taken to improve the activities of this institution, its financial and economic condition, income and expenses, and the use of budgetary, extra-budgetary, sponsorship, and other funds. The board organizes collaborative work with the institution's teachers to improve the quality of education within the institution.

Carries out the tasks assigned to the head of the state preschool educational organization regarding the measures taken to improve the activities of this organization, the financial and economic condition, income and expenses, the use of budgetary, extrabudgetary, sponsorship, and other funds. Organizes collaborative work with the organization's teachers to improve the quality of education within the organization.

- **Keywords: strategic body, strategic plan, budget, inviolability, transparency.**

- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" states that the pedagogical council in preschool educational organizations is a collegial body of the organization, and the supervisory board determines the priority directions for the development of state preschool educational organizations.

- The procedure for maintaining the documentation of the supervisory board in preschool educational organizations is one of the important management elements, allowing for transparency of the organization's activities, setting goals, and monitoring their achievement.

- The main goals and objectives of the supervisory board established in preschool educational organizations are as follows.

- Including:

- to elect the director of the organization from among the candidates recommended by the territorial department, as well as to submit proposals for their dismissal from the position held;

- Defining priority areas for the development of the organization;

- to hear reports from the director of the organization on the work carried out to improve the organization's activities, financial and economic situation, income and expenses, and the use of budgetary, extra-budgetary, and sponsorship funds;

- Reviewing the organization's annual financial plans, the prices of paid services provided, and the amount of rent for the use of the organization's property, including the

starting price at auctions, in the presence of the organization's director and providing recommendations;

- Conducting social surveys on the activities of the director, pedagogical and other employees of the organization;
- Providing practical assistance in cooperation with parents, public organizations, and sponsors to create and improve favorable conditions for pupils in the organization;
- Submitting proposals to the territorial department regarding the educational organization director's programs and plans to determine priority areas for the organization's development;
- Submitting proposals to the territorial department for incentivizing the organization's employees.

The Council may perform other functions in accordance with the legislation.

The activities of the supervisory board, established in the organization to provide children with quality education, create appropriate conditions for them, and support the educational process, are organized in the following manner.

The Supervisory Board is formed from parents or guardians of pupils in each group, teachers, assistant educators, the administration of the preschool educational organization, and employees of the territorial department. The number of members must be an odd number of at least 11 people. The Council includes 2 members from among the organization's teachers, 2 from among the teacher's assistants, 1 from the organization's administration, 1 from the relevant territorial department, 2 from public organizations and sponsors, and at least 3 members from the parents of pupils in each group.

The number of Council members is not limited.

The Chairman and Secretary of the Council are elected by a simple majority through open voting among the total number of members present at the first meeting of the Council. The chairman and secretary of the Council are elected from among the parents who are Council members.

The composition of the Council is elected for a period of 3 years. The composition of the Council may be reviewed at the beginning of each academic year.

Parents of children in the organization or their guardians (one of them) may participate in the election of Council members.

Members of the Council are elected by open vote at the general meeting of parents of the organization's pupils.

When children of parents elected as Council members are removed from the list of pupils in the organization, this Council member is also removed from the Council, and another member is elected from among the parents to take their place.

Employees of the organization's administration, teachers, educators, and assistant educators are elected to the organization's pedagogical council by secret ballot and approved by the decision of the organization's pedagogical council.

A representative of the territorial department is appointed as a member of the Council by order of the relevant district preschool education department.

The head of the organization or their deputies, as well as their close relatives, are not allowed to be elected as members of the Council.

If a Council member is absent from Council meetings three times consecutively without valid reasons, they are removed from the Council membership.

The first meeting of the Council is organized and conducted by the director of the organization.

The Council meets at least once a quarter.

Council meetings are documented in minutes.

The Council can make decisions at a meeting when 60 percent of its total members are present.

The Council carries out its activities in accordance with the principles of inviolability, openness, transparency, and fairness.

Council decisions are made by a simple majority vote based on the equality of its members. In the event of a tie, the Chairman of the Council has the casting vote.

Council meetings are chaired by the Chairman of the Council.

In cases where the Chairman of the Council is temporarily unable to perform their duties (during a business trip, vacation, or illness), the performance of their duties is temporarily assigned to one of the Council members. In this case, it cannot be assigned to employees of the organization or territorial departments.

➤ The director of the organization or their deputies may participate in the Council meeting as observers.

➤ The Chairman of the Council is responsible for organizing and conducting Council meetings in accordance with the requirements of this Regulation, as well as for the correct and complete preparation of documents.

➤ Council members must be notified of the date, time, place, and issues to be discussed at least 10 days before the Council meeting. The Chairman of the Council is responsible for informing the Council members.

➤ The Director of the organization is responsible for holding Council meetings and organizing its work (providing a room necessary for processing and storing documents, information related to the organization's activities, and office supplies).

➤ It is recommended to post information on the Council's activities quarterly on the organization's official website, in the media, or in a place visible to all in the organization.

➤ Minutes of Council meetings must be submitted to the territorial department within a period not exceeding 3 days from the date of the Council meeting.

➤ The Council, in carrying out its assigned tasks, has the following rights:

➤ To request and receive information from the head of the organization on the organization's activities for the relevant period;

➤ To review the organization's financial statements;

➤ To examine information on the receipt and expenditure of sponsorship and charitable funds;

➤ To submit proposals for protecting the honor, dignity, and reputation of the organization's teaching staff.

Interference in the activities of the Council by the director of the organization, regional department, local authorities, and other organizations is not permitted.

Collection of funds from pupils and their parents for various reasons by the director of the organization, members of the Council, and other employees is strictly prohibited.

Persons found guilty of violating the requirements of the Regulation shall be held accountable in accordance with the procedure established by law.

The Council organizes its activities in accordance with the principles of inviolability, openness, transparency, and fairness. The proper formation of the Supervisory Board's composition, defining the tasks of the board members within their authority, improving the material and technical base of the preschool educational organization, and providing visual didactic materials to enhance the quality of education are the functions carried out by the Supervisory Board.

The procedure for maintaining documents of the supervisory board in state preschool educational organizations is determined by general legislation and internal regulations. This procedure helps ensure the transparency, effectiveness, and accountability of the supervisory board's activities. The decisions and recommendations adopted by the Supervisory Board, as well as official protocols, should provide important administrative conclusions for the work and development of the organization.

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